

due to the presence of shorter conjugated chain for resonance while the compound No. 2 shows deep coloured fluorescence due to the presence of long conjugated chain for resonance (according to E. R. Watson theory of color).

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Phytochemical Studies on *Salvia coccinea* Linn

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In view of the high medicinal importance and utility of *Salvia species*¹ (Family-Labiata) in various ailments such as diarrhoea, haemorrhoids, lung diseases, gangrene etc., a systematic chemical investigation of *Salvia coccinea*² Linn. on which no phytochemical work seems to have been done so far, has been undertaken in this laboratory. It is a slender herb, 1-2 ft. high; native of S. America. It also grows between 3500-7000 ft. in the West Himalayas.

The air dried powdered whole plant of *S. coccinea* (1.5 Kg.) was extracted successively with petroleum ether (60°-80°) and benzene.

Petroleum ether concentrate was subjected to chromatography over Brockmann alumina. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) mixture yielded a compound (0.02 gm.) which on crystallisation from acetone gave a colourless solid m.p. 84°-85°. The I. R. spectrum of the solid discloses its alcoholic nature (ν_{\max} . 3300 cm^{-1} associated-OH). The mass spectrum of the compound in addition to molecular ion peak at m/e 452, exhibits ion peaks at m/e 434 (M-18) and m/e 31 (-CH₂OH). The physical properties of the compound were found to be very similar to those reported for n-hentriacontanol³ which was finally confirmed by the direct comparison (m.m.p., Co.T.L.C. & CO.I.R.) with an authentic sample of n-hentriacontanol.

Elution with benzene afforded a product (0.15 gm.) which on crystallisation from methanol gave shining white flakes, m.p. 134°-136°. It showed bluish-violet colouration with Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol (ν_{\max} . 3560 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl and 1649 cm^{-1} for unsaturation). The mass spectrum of the compound recorded fragment ion peaks at m/e 396 (M-18), 273 (M-side chain, C₁₀H₂₁) and m/e 255 [(M-18)-side chain. i. e., C₁₀H₂₁], besides the molecular ion peak at m/e 414. It forms an acetate m.p. 128° and a benzoate, m.p. 142°. The identity of the compound as β -sitosterol has been established by m.m.p. determination, Co-T.L.C. and CO.I.R. with the authentic specimen of the compound.

Further elution with benzene furnished a very small quantity (0.005 gm.) of another crystalline solid, m.p. 210°-212°, which responds to positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for triterpene. Further characterisation of the compound was not possible due to paucity of the material.

The benzene extract on chromatography over Brockmann alumina in the usual way afforded only β -sitosterol in the benzene chloroform (1:1) eluate.

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Chemical Constituents of *Rumex orientalis* Bernh

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RUMEX orientalis Bernh. syn. *Rumex patiens* Linn, a native of Europe, is found in Western Himalayas from Kumaon to Kashmir. Its roots are reported to be used as purgative¹, and are known to contain some anthraquinone derivatives². A survey.

of the literature shows that chrysophanic acid and rheochrysidin (physcion) have already been isolated from *R. orientalis*³. In the present paper, we report the isolation of nepodin (I), tricosanol (II), β -sitosterol (III) and emodin (IV) from the roots of this plant.

Pet. ether (60°-80°) extract of air-dried powdered roots was subjected to silicagel chromatography. Elution with Pet. ether-benzene (4 : 1) yielded compound (I) which crystallised as pale yellow needles from *n*-hexane m.p. 162°-163°. NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.52 s, -CH₃ protons ; 2.64 s, -COCH₃ protons ; 6.84 s, 4-H ; 7.44 d (J=9 Hz), 5-H and a multiplet between 6.8 and 7.0 due to 6-H and 7-H. MS : M⁺ 216 and other prominent peaks at m/e 201, 198, 155, 127 and 115. Its identity was finally confirmed as nepodin by mmp, Co-TLC and superposable IR. Diacetate m.p. 186-7°, identical with nepodin diacetate (CO-TLC, IR and mmp).

Further elution of the column led to the isolation of chrysophanic acid (Pet. ether-benzene 4 : 1) and physcion (Pet. ether-benzene 3 : 2). Combined benzene and benzene-chloroform (1 : 3) eluates yielded a residue giving positive L.B. test. This on rechromatography over silicagel column afforded compound (II) m. p. 73°-74° (Pet ether-benzene 3 : 1), which was identified as tricosanol (mmp and Co-TLC) by comparison with an authentic sample. Pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate yielded compound (III), m.p. 136°, identified as β -sitosterol by CO-TLC, IR and mmp.

Ether extract of the powdered roots was chromatographed over a silica gel column. Benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluate furnished compound (IV) m.p. 253-255°. It was identified as emodin by mmp, CO-TLC, superposable IR, NMR and MS which were identical with that reported for emodin⁴.

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Some 6:8-Dichloro-S-Substituted-2-Mercapto-3-Aryl (or Alkyl)-4-Quinazolones

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IN view of the broad spectrum biological activities associated with 4-quinazolones¹⁻⁵, it seemed of interest to synthesize 6 : 8-dichloro-s-substituted-2-mercapto-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-quinazolone derivatives and evaluate them for their activities. The therapeutic effect of 4-quinazolone derivatives has been demonstrated in the case of siamian and avian malarial infections. The anticonvulsant properties of QZ-2(2-methyl-3-*o*-tolyl-4-quinazolone, available commercially as Melsedin) have been reported in mice, rats and dogs⁶⁻⁹. A potent anticonvulsant property of BDH 1880 (2-methyl-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-quinazolone hydrochloride) has been reported against matrazole induced convulsions in mice¹⁰.

The above findings have led the authors to synthesize some 6 : 8-dichloro-2-thio-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-quinazolones by condensing aryl or alkyl-isothiocyanates with 3 : 5-dichloro-anthranilic acid in dry ethanol, and alkylating these 4(3H)-quinazolones with alkyl halides in alcoholic alkaline solution. That the alkylation occurred at the sulphur rather than the nitrogen atom was proved for a representative member of the series by hydrolysis to the corresponding mercaptan.

Experimental

6 : 8-Dichloro-2-thio-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-quinazolones were prepared as described earlier¹¹.

6 : 8-Dichloro-2-(*N*, *N*-benzylphenylcarboxamidomethylthio)-3-phenyl-4-(3-*H*)quinazolone : 6:8-Dichloro-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4-(3H) quinazolone (3.2 g) was dissolved in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution and filtered. In the filtrate, *N*-benzylchloroacetanilide (2.8 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol was added and the mixture was stirred vigorously for one hour at room temperature. The crystalline product obtained was filtered, washed 3 or 4 times with water and then with a little ethanol. Finally it was recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 142°, yield 50%. (Found : N, 7.42 ; S, 5.66. C₂₉H₂₁Cl₂N₃O₂S requires N, 7.69 ; S, 5.86%),

Similarly, other 6 : 8-Dichloro-2-(*N,N*-disubstitutedcarboxamidomethylthio)-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-(3H) quinazolones were prepared. They were crystallized from ethanol. Their yields, melting points and analytical results are recorded in Table 1.